

Bahinabai Chaudhari's Songs: A Performance Tradition in Maharashtra

also known as “Grindmill Songs”, “Women's Work Songs”, “Ovi”, “Folk Songs”

Secondary source

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* Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA

Entry tags: Religious Group, Vaishnavism, Hinduism, Bhakti

Bahinabai Chaudhari, popularly remembered as Bahinai, was born in an agrarian village in the Jalgaon district of Maharashtra. She had three sisters and three brothers and was married off at the age of 13 to a Vatandar (landowning farmer) - Nathuji Chaudhari. Nathuji was 30 when he married Bahinai; Bahinai was 30 when she was widowed. Bahinai could not read or write. She spent most of her life toiling in farms and kitchens; as a widow, she did the same with the additional burden of clearing her husband's financial debt. In this context of everyday labor, Bahinai sang a genre of song called ovi - short, rhyming, rhythmic couplets. She sang in the Khandeshi-Varhadi dialect of Marathi (also called Ahirani). Her songs were preserved and published posthumously by her son, Sopandev, and have since been a topic of academic writing and popular representation in films and school textbooks. Of the many themes that these songs address, Bahinai's devotion and love (bhakti) for Vitthal (an avatar of Krishna worshipped by Varkaris) is persistent. I, therefore, think that exploring her performance tradition in the disciplinary context of religion could raise important questions - what were the different ways of worshipping Vitthal in Bahinai's immediate context? Why did she sing ovis in the midst of everyday labor like grinding grain and threshing wheat? Are these activities 'religious' or 'folk' or both or neither? Do larger categories like Hinduism elucidate Bahinai's songs at all? And what are the gendered aspects of this genre - in terms of its history and contemporary practice? The following questionnaire is a rudimentary attempt to address these questions.

Date Range: 1880 CE - 1951 CE

Region: Asoda, Maharashtra, India

Region tags: South Asia, India, Western India

The main regions in India where Bahinabai's songs are sung and remembered.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Chaudhari, Bahinabai. Bahinaichi Gani. Mumbai: Suchitra Prakashan, 2012.
- Source 2: Suryavamshi, Ramesh. Ahirani Shabdakosh (Ahirani-Marathi): Ahiranibolicha Pahila Shabdakosh. Aurangabad: Abhyasika Prakashan, 2013.
- Source 3: Chaudhari, Snehalata. Bhoomikanya Bahinabai Chaudhari: Ek Chintan. Pune: Continental

Prakashan, 2002.

Notes: These sources are written in Marathi. Source 1 is an exhaustive collection of Bahinai's songs. Source 2 is a dictionary. Source 3 is a critical reflection on Bahinai's songs, written by a member of her family.

- Source 1: Purohit, Anjali. Ragi Ragini: Chronicles from Aji's Kitchen. Mumbai: Yoda Press, 2012.
- Source 2: Bhagwat, A. R. "Maharashtrian Folk-Songs on the Grindmill." *Journal of the University of Bombay* 10 (1941): 134-86; Fuller, Mary. "Marathi Grinding Songs." *The New Review* 11 (1940): 382-92, 508-520; Shukla, Rohini. "Authorship and Generative Embodiment in Bahinai's Songs." *Transnational Literature* 10 (2018): 1-15.
- Source 3: Poitevin, Guy and Hema Rairkar. *Stonemill and Bhakti: From the Devotion of Peasant Women to the Philosophy of Swamis*. New Delhi: D.K. Printworld, 1996.

Notes: These sources are written in English. Source 1 is a recipe book interspersed with translations of Bahinai's songs. Source 2 are essays on grindmill songs in Maharashtra. Source 3 is a book on grindmill songs in Maharashtra, and has relevant information for those interested in the history of these songs.

- Source 1: Bahinai. Directed by Atul Pethe. Pune: Atul Pethe Productions, 2014.
- Source 2: Hatekar, Neelam. *Bahinabai*. Nagpur: Shree Mangesh Prakashan, 2010; Deshmukh, Bhagwant. *Dagdi Jatyaca Reshmi Gala*. Pune: Pratima Prakashan, 2000; Jagnale, Rekha. *Nirashakanya Bahinabainche Kavyashilpa*. Nagpur: Vijay Prakashan, 2012.
- Source 3: Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkaranchya Aathvaninche Aatmabhan by Hema Rairkar; Mahayogini Bahinabai by Leela Patil; Bahinabai: Dhyas ani Abhyas by Indrajit Bhalerao.

Notes: These sources are in Marathi. Source 1 is a documentary. It provides a detailed picture of Bahinai's material context (farm plantations, domestic activities, etc.) and how women continue to sing her songs today. The film has English subtitles, insightful interviews with Bahinai's family members, and ends with interviews by two eminent Marathi scholars - N. D. Mahanor, Bhalchandra Nemade. Source 2 are books in Marathi. Information on Source 3 is incomplete.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://grindmill.org/>
- Source 1 Description: This project documents and translates (into English and French) grindmill songs.
- Source 2 URL: <http://nmu.ac.in/bcsrc/en-us/home.aspx>
- Source 2 Description: This is a university in Jalgaon dedicated to the study of Bahinai's songs.
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rQ9OUQzm0k>
- Source 3 Description: This is a song from the Marathi film *Manini* (1961). The lyrics are composed by Bahinai.
- Source 1 URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=o_FrJhYyljk
- Source 1 Description: These are songs from a Marathi biopic of Bahinai called 'Sopanchi Aai Bahinabai' (2013/2014?).
- Source 2 URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zOCTecfBm_A
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oJWqslL-XvA>

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/i40039215>

– Source 1 Description: Philip Engblom, Jayant Karve and Maxine Berntsen translated four of Bahinabai's songs in 1982. A brief introduction to Bahinabai by Eleanor Zelliot was also published in this volume.

– Source 2 URL: http://fhrc.flinders.edu.au/transnational/vol8_issue1.html

– Source 2 Description: This is an English translation of one ovi, with a brief introduction to Bahinai.

– Source 3 URL: <http://www.jstor.org/action/doBasicSearch?Query=au%3A%22Bahinaabaai+Choudhari%22>

– Source 3 Description: Under the search title 'Bahinaabaai Choudhari,' one can find several translations by Shubhada Rani Kaul published in 2004.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Bahinai's songs are part of a public cultural memory - they do not, in and of themselves, belong to a specific religious group; those who do participate in this public memory, also, do not by virtue of their participation form a religious group. The genre of grindmill songs has existed and flourished in varied languages and religious contexts (inside and outside Maharashtra) - Bahinai worshipped Vitthal, who is considered a Hindu deity, but there are ample examples of grindmill songs in Islamic and Christian contexts. See Eaton, Richard Maxwell. *Sufis of Bijapur, 1300-1700: Social Roles of Sufis in Medieval India*. (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1978) 160-80; Fuller, Mary. "Marathi Grinding Songs." *The New Review* 11 (1940): 382-92; Jassal, Smita Tewari. *Unearthing Gender: Folksongs of North India*. (London: Duke University Press, 2012).

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Bahinai did not have official or unofficial political support. See Schultz, Anna. *Singing a Hindu Nation: Marathi Devotional Performance and Nationalism*. Chicago: OUP, 2012. Compare how kirtan performance was affected by nationalism in urban Maharashtra, and how ovi performance in rural Maharashtra remained relatively unaffected.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Bahinai repudiated two crucial aspects of Vitthal bhakti in her immediate context - vari (a

pilgrimage in which devotees walk for several days toward Vitthal's temple in Pandharpur) and kirtan (a genre of devotional performance most famously performed by and attributed to Saint Namdev). I hesitate to term Bahinai's devotional practices as 'acts of apostasy' because she did not explicitly declare 'public abandonment'. Bahinai simply expressed her devotion differently by singing a unique form of ovi (in new spaces and in the midst of new activities). For more on kirtan read Novetzke, Christian. *Religion and Public Memory: A Cultural History of Saint Namdev in India*. New York: Columbia University Press, 2008. For more on vari read Karve, I. "On the Road: A Maharashtrian Pilgrimage." *The Journal of Asian Studies* 22 (1962): 13-29. doi: 10.2307/2049906.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Field doesn't know

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Bahinai popularized a particular style of performance, and hence the eponymously named genre - Bahinaichi gani. This does not imply that she is the 'leader.'

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: Bahinai could not read or write. She is known to have never regarded any one written text or scripture as authoritative. The history of ovi does, however, foreground the importance of early Marathi texts. The *Lilacaritra* (1278) mentions women singing ovis in the midst of everyday labor on several occasions, and the *Jnesvari* (1290) is written in the ovi meter. The two texts - the *Lilacaritra* and the *Jnesvari* - are regarded as sacred texts by Mahanubhavs and Varkaris. What ovi means in these varied textual and performative contexts remains to be explored in detail.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1880 CE - 2016 CE

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Notes: Bahinai's songs in particular and grindmill songs in general are sung in 'private' spaces (and spaces like farms that do not easily fit into the public-private dichotomy).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1880 CE - 2016 CE

Region: District Khandesh, Maharashtra, India.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: See comment on apostasy.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1880 CE - 2016 CE

Region: District Khandesh, Maharashtra, India.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Notes: Bahinai does not seem to believe in karma - the belief that god or an organizing cosmic principle is keeping an account of one's good and bad deeds, and that all deeds have calculated consequences which are meted out across lifetimes. Her songs emphasize the human ability to deliberate and act self-consciously; she often questions conventional ideas of the good and the bad.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Notes: See previous comment.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Bahinai was highly critical of Brahminical and patriarchal norms.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Bahinai's moral outlook is a rich topic awaiting scholarly exploration. Values such as honesty and simplicity are often exalted in her songs; as I have mentioned earlier, she condemns violence against women and caste discrimination.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: Bahinai's songs are usually sung while working in kitchens or farms, and therefore, hard physical labor is almost always coeval with singing. Bahinai sings about how singing alleviates the pains of physical labor, and how physical labor, in turn, motivates the act of singing.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– Yes

Notes: See previous comment.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Bahinai (1880-1951) lived through India's transition from a British colony to an independent nation-state (in 1947).

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: I have in mind the nexus of government/private schools and colleges in Maharashtra. Although formal education is in principle available, the literacy rate remains low, especially in rural Maharashtra. Bahinai was herself illiterate.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: See previous comment.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherent's interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: There is no bureaucracy within the group.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: As would any member of a nation-state, it is likely that residents interact with institutional

bureaucracies like the police, tax collectors, and so on.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: As i have mentioned before, Bahinai's songs are sung while working in kitchens and farms. This covers a wide spectrum of food preparation - from sowing seeds to harvesting, to grinding wheat flour, to roasting bhakri (a type of bread).

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No